

Optimal Node Design in Filterless Horseshoe Networks with Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers

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Abstract—Point-to-multipoint coherent transceivers are an efficient solution for the hub-and-spoke traffic pattern of metro-aggregation networks. This paper proposes a framework to optimize amplifier placement and node configuration selection in filterless horseshoe metro-aggregation networks. The results obtained provide insight into the extent of amplifier savings.

Keywords—point-to-multipoint transceivers, optical amplifiers

I. INTRODUCTION

Metro-aggregation networks play a critical role in the overall communications infrastructure. Sitting between access networks and metro-core networks, they feature specific requirements, such as a hub-and-spoke traffic pattern (as in access networks), survivability to single failures (as in metro-core and regional networks) and total capacity requirements between those of the network segments they interface with. Survivability to single failures can be attained via a horseshoe topology and connecting each leaf node to two different hub nodes [1]. The emergence of point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers using digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM), which are able to connect multiple lower capacity devices at the leaf nodes to a single high capacity device at a hub node [2], has a twofold benefit: (1) they are a natural fit to hub-and-spoke traffic pattern and (2) they offer a more cost-effective migration from direct detect to coherent channels, when compared to traditional point-to-point coherent transceivers [2], [3]. Further simplification of metro-aggregation networks is possible by adopting a filterless architecture, which replaces active filter cards by power splitters and combiners, and by selective deployment of optical amplifiers. The authors' work in [1] proposes an integer linear programming (ILP) model to design filterless horseshoe networks using P2MP transceivers, which aims to minimize the number of amplifiers required while ensuring that several end-to-end performance thresholds are still met. The work in [1] assumes leaf nodes are customizable by selecting each splitter and combiner from a catalogue. Although this allows fine tuning the power budget and maximizing the amplifier savings, it demands using discrete components and a more complex and error-prone deployment.

This work extends the previous ILP model to consider single and per direction node configurations, which facilitates having integrated solutions that have lower cost and are easier to deploy. The impact of different candidate node architectures is evaluated using the proposed ILP model to design multiple filterless horseshoe metro-aggregation networks.

II. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

In a filterless horseshoe network supporting connectivity to two hub nodes located at both ends of the horseshoe, each fiber carries downstream traffic from one hub node and upstream traffic towards the other hub node (e.g., Fig. 1 in [1]). Hence, each leaf node comprises one splitter and one combiner per transmission direction (total of four devices). It is assumed that a pre-amplifier can be present in each direction and minimizing the number of these devices is the main optimization objective. The receiver sensitivity constraint, the launch power threshold to ensure negligible impact of nonlinear interference (NLI) and the maximum power unbalance between subcarriers (SCs) at the hub's receiver are modelled as constraints of the model. Tables I and II present the main input parameters and the variables of the ILP model, respectively.

TABLE I. MODEL INPUT PARAMETERS

Parameter	Description and values assumed
$G(V, E)$	graph with leaf nodes $u, v \in V$ and links $l \in E$
$W(u)$	length of the link preceding leaf u
α	fiber attenuation coefficient (0.22 dB/km)
$G_s(g)$	amplifier gain, $\{0, 6, 7, \dots, 20\}$ dB, where g is the gain index
P_{sc}	transmitter launch power per SC (-12 dBm)
P_n	power threshold for negligible NLI per SC (-10 dBm)
P_s	receiver sensitivity for 16QAM signal (-24 dBm)
P_l	maximum power difference between SCs at the hub (8 dB)
$H(s, p)$	insertion loss of node configuration s at port p

TABLE II. MODEL VARIABLES

Variable	Description
\mathbb{V}_s^u	binary variable for configuration selection per leaf node
δ_p^u	loss of port p of configuration selected for leaf node u
μ_g^u	binary variable to determine if amplifier at u takes gain g
ϕ_u^1	hub 2 receiver power per SC coming from leaf node u
ϕ_u^2	leaf node u receiver power per SC coming from hub 1
ϵ_1 / ϵ_2	lower / upper bound of variables ϕ_u^1

The primary objective function of the ILP model (1) is to minimize the number of amplifiers. It also includes a secondary objective to minimize the difference of SC power levels at the hub 2 receiver (to optimize performance). The weight factor w enforces this strict prioritization. Constraint (2) assigns losses to the different ports, whereas constraints (3) and (4) express the power levels from leaf nodes to hub 2 and from hub 1 to leaf nodes, respectively. The power threshold at fiber input to limit NLI impact is set by constraints (5) and (6) when considering the direction from the leaf nodes to hub 2 and from hub 1 to leaf nodes, respectively. Node configuration and amplifier selection are determined by constraints (7) and (8). Constraints (9) to (11)

$$\min \sum_u \sum_{G_e(g) \neq 0} \mu_u^g + w[\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1] \quad (1)$$

$$\delta_p^u = \sum_s \nabla_s^u H(s, p), \quad \forall u \in V \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_u^1 = P_{sc} + \sum_{v>u} G_e(g) \mu_g^u - \alpha \sum_{v>u} W(v) - \delta_{p_3}^u - \sum_{v>u} \sum_{p \in (p_2, p_4)} \delta_p^v, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_u^2 = P_{sc} + \sum_{v<u} G_e(g) \mu_g^u - \alpha \sum_{v<u} W(v) - \delta_{p_1}^u - \sum_{v<u} \sum_{p \in (p_2, p_4)} \delta_p^v, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (4)$$

$$P_{sc} + \sum_{u_p < v \leq u} \sum_g G_e(g) \mu_v^g - \alpha \sum_{u_p < v \leq u} W(u) - \delta_{p_3}^u - \sum_{u_p < v \leq u} \sum_{p \in (p_2, p_4)} \delta_p^v \leq P_n, \quad \forall u, u_p \in V \quad (5)$$

$$P_{sc} + \sum_{v \leq u} \sum_g G_e(g) \mu_v^g - \alpha \sum_{v \leq u} W(u) - \sum_{v \leq u} \sum_{p \in (p_2, p_4)} \delta_p^v \leq P_n, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_s \nabla_s^u = 1, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_g \mu_g^u = 1, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon_1 \leq \phi_u^1, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (9)$$

$$\epsilon_2 \geq \phi_u^2, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1 \leq P_l \quad (11)$$

$$\phi_{u'}^1 \phi_u^2 \geq P_s, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (12)$$

are used to calculate the lower and upper bound of the SC power levels at hub 2 and to ensure the maximum SC power difference is met. Finally, the receiver sensitivity constraint is expressed by (12). Note that a constraint for the required optical signal-to-noise ratio at the receiver is not included in the model since it is not possible to express it using only linear terms. Hence, for practical purposes it must be verified outside of the ILP model.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The described ILP model can be used to design a generic filterless horseshoe network exploiting DSCM-based P2MP coherent transceivers. Moreover, as the model is parameterized per SC, the outcome is valid when considering different number of SCs are allocated to the leaf nodes, assuming the number of transceivers at the hub and leaf nodes does not change. A key input impacting the number of optical amplifiers required is the available node configurations, which determine the losses of express, add and drop signals. Table III shows the baseline set of possible node configurations, which can favor (in terms of signal power losses) certain paths inside the node at the expense of others. This is attained using devices with different splitting ratios. For the specific loss values, please refer to [1].

TABLE III. NODE CONFIGURATIONS

Splitter (express : drop)	Combiner (add : express)	Rationale
50 : 50	50 : 50	Reference case (balanced losses)
80 : 20	20 : 80	Favor express at the expense of equally add and drop
70 : 30	30 : 70	Favor express and prefer drop over add
70 : 30	10 : 90	Favor express and prefer add over drop
90 : 10	30 : 70	Favor drop at the expense of add
30 : 70	30 : 70	Favor add at the expense of drop

Two main node deployment scenarios are considered. The first assumes that the configuration is selected per transmission direction, which means the configuration used at a given leaf node for the direction from hub 1 to hub 2 can be different from that used for the direction from hub 2 to hub 1. This is denoted as D-config and allows running the ILP model independently for each direction. The second scenario assumes that the node must use the same configuration in both directions and is designated as N-config. It requires integrating both transmission directions into a single ILP model. Moreover, for each scenario, the list of available node configurations includes all the ones in Table III (Full), the sub-set of the first four configurations (Balanced & Exp), only the 50 : 50 (Balanced), only the 70 : 30 combined with 30 : 70 (Exp70), only the 30 : 70 combined with 30 : 70

(Drop70) and only the 70 : 30 combined with 70 : 30 (Add70). In the case of the later four sets, since they have only a single configuration, D-config and N-config scenarios are the same.

A total of 50 horseshoe networks with 10 leaf nodes were randomly generated using a span length distribution that was derived from realistic metro-aggregation networks [1]. The results presented are the average value from running the ILP model in all the horseshoe networks. Table IV shows the number of optical amplifiers required (N) and the worst-case SC power difference at the receiver of the hub nodes (Δ_{\max}).

TABLE IV. RESULTS IN A 10-NODE FILTERLESS HORSESHOE NETWORK

Configuration Set	Scenario	N	Δ_{\max}
Full	N-config	9.08	2.64 dB
	D-config	8.72	1.81 dB
Balanced & Exp	N-config	9.40	2.89 dB
	D-config	9.08	2.30 dB
Balanced	N-config	17.76	1.55 dB
	Exp70	11.20	7.19 dB
Drop70	N-config	18.00	0.70 dB
Add70	N-config	18.00	0.70 dB

As expected, the results show that having a larger number of node configurations to select from can lead to larger amplifier savings, which can be half of those required when only balanced splitter/combiner devices are available (8.72 vs. 17.76). Still, most of the benefits can be realized with four out of the seven configurations (e.g., 9.08 vs 8.72). In the considered cases, the extra flexibility of D-config compared to N-config only allowed savings of up to 4% in the number of amplifiers, which suggests that the potential of N-config for further integration and to reduce the number of deployable items likely makes it a better solution. When considering a single configuration, the results highlight that out of the four cases evaluated, only Exp70 still enables significant reductions in amplifier count, demanding around 28% more amplifiers than Full, D-config. Nevertheless, this solution has a more limited ability to mitigate the SC power level unbalance at the receiver of the hub nodes.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Hosseini, et al., "Optimized physical design of metro aggregation networks using point-to-multipoint transceivers," OFC 2022, W3F.2.
- [2] D. Welch, et al., "Digital subcarrier multiplexing: Enabling software-configurable optical networks," Journal of Lightwave Technology, vol. 41, pp. 1175-1191, February 2022.
- [3] M. Hosseini, et al., "Optimization of survivable filterless optical networks exploiting digital subcarrier multiplexing," Journal of Optical Communications and Networking, vol. 14, pp. 586-594, July 2022.